

Table 1. The major agronomic characters of Bright-pearl 1.

Site	Sowing (month/day)	Planting method ^a	80% heading (month/day)	Growth duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Seed set (%)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Hangzhou, Zhejiang	7/8	TP	9/18	112	85.2	69.9	88.6	7.64
	7/15	BS	9/19	107	82.5	72.8	83.2	6.95
	6/16	DS	8/24	106	89.7	62.6	92.3	7.25
	7/10	DS	9/14	96	85.9	65.1	86.7	6.81
	7/25	DS	9/24	92	81.5	64.2	84.7	6.43
Jiaxing, Zhejiang	7/10	BS	9/11	103	87.5	77.2	85.6	6.48
Ningbo, Zhejiang	6/20	TP	9/3	115	90.2	76.5	89.5	8.21
Tanzhou, Zhejiang	7/10	TP	9/15	107	84.6	78.9	84.3	7.82
Dangtu, Aihui	6/24	TP	9/2	106	87.0	71.6	85.1	7.13
Nanlin, Aihui	6/30	TP	9/15	120	92.7	74.6	91.2	7.50
Jinshan, Shanghai	5/27	TP	8/25	136	98.0	78.0	89.7	7.13
Nantong, Jiangsu	5/20	TP	8/25	133	95.4	71.4	93.4	6.69
Xingfeng, Jiangxi	6/30	DS	9/5	105	99.5	80.5	94.3	9.99

^aTP = transplanting, BS = broadcast seeding, DS = direct sowing.

Table 2. Milled rice properties of Bright-pearl 1.

Variety	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Shape L/W	Chalkiness (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Alkali spreading value	Amylose content	Unbroken milled rice (%)
Bright-pearl 1	4.9	2.9	1.7	0.5	26.2	6.7	16.3	75.9
Xiushui 11 (check)	5.3	3.0	1.7	7.0	27.5	7.0	15.6	64.7

a late japonica cultivar that resists bacterial blight (BB) and blast. Bright-pearl 1 is a photoperiod-sensitive japonica rice with blast, BB, and BPH resistance. Its growth duration is about 135 d for a single crop and about 100 d for late season direct sowing in Zhejiang, Aihui, and Shanghai.

The major agronomic characters were recorded (Table 1). Bright-pearl 1 has ideal plant type, with erect leaves, suitable stem angles, a strong root system, and tolerance for lodging. It also has good rice quality (Table 2). Bright-pearl 1 can be used in japonica rice breeding and can be planted by farmers. ■

Crop and resource management

Physiology and plant nutrition

Growth characteristics of IRRI-developed new rice plant type breeding lines in Japan

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IRRI recently developed breeding lines of a new rice plant type (NPT) that promises increased yield potential in the tropics. These lines are tropical japonicas that have fewer but larger panicles than current modern varieties. They are known as panicle weight types. The physiological basis for the increased yield of the lines, however, has not been elucidated.

We conducted field experiments at NARC to examine the factors related to the

yield potential of these NPT lines. Two NPT lines provided by IRRI and four cultivars (Table 1) were transplanted in 1994 during mid-May and mid-June. Planting density was 26.7 hills m⁻² and 180 kg N ha⁻¹ was applied (80 kg as basal, 60 kg at panicle initiation, and 40 kg during mid-reproductive phase). Standard management practices were followed.

The dry weight of each organ and the leaf area were monitored at three growth stages for 15 plants. Yield and its components were observed in three replicated plots. The average solar radiation and average temperature during the growing season were higher than normal, contributing to good growth. Damage from disease and insect pests was minimal. Necrosis of the axis of the panicle and rachis in IR66740-ACI-3 plants was observed during the late ripening phase.

The NPT lines grew slowly initially, but the rate during the reproductive phase was faster than that of the other cultivars. Dry weight at heading was almost the same for

the test materials, although it was sometimes higher for the NPT lines. However, the biological yield of the NPT lines was lower than that of most of the cultivars because the increase in their dry weight after heading was lower. Panicle number of the NPT lines was low, and IR65598-112-2 was the lowest. The spikelet number panicle⁻¹ of IR65598-112-2 was the highest among the materials tested (Table 1).

Leaves of both NPT lines were erect during the ripening phase, which ensured better canopy structure. No lodging was observed in NPT lines although most of the other cultivars from both plantings lodged during the mid-ripening phase (Table 1).

Sink size was calculated by multiplying filled grain weight by spikelet number. No significant difference was found between the sink size of the NPT lines and most of the cultivars, although their economic yield was the lowest due to a lower grain-filling percentage (Table 2).

The reduced percentage of filled grains was attributed to the grain sink being

Table 1. Growth characteristics of new plant type lines compared with those of high-yielding cultivars. Yawara, Japan. 1994.

Cultivar/line	Days to heading ^a (no.)	Biological yield ^b (g m ⁻²)	SD ^c	Specific leaf area ^d (cm ² g ⁻¹)	Leaf area index ^d	Panicle number (no. m ⁻¹)	Spikelet number (no. panicle ⁻¹)	LB/TDW ^e	NSC ^f content (%)	ADWr ^g (g m ⁻²)	Lodging score ^h
<i>May transplanting</i>											
IR65598-112-2	89	1737	146	185	7.2	144	367	0.33	39.1	392	0
IR66740-AC1-3	92	1605	344	180	9.0	317	131	0.37	31.8	150	0
Kochihibiki	77	1539	104	217	6.5	499	70	0.30	10.5	474	3.2
Takanari	82	2006	65	206	7.0	281	182	0.28	10.8	786	0
IR36	85	1800	60	232	6.6	580	88	0.27	6.8	645	4
IR72	88	1753	137	212	8.2	501	109	0.32	4.7	458	3.5
<i>June transplanting</i>											
IR65598-112-2	76	1494	2	159	4.6	118	326	0.29	13.8	444	0
IR66740-AC1-3	85	1625	139	171	7.5	217	171	0.36	34.9	305	0
Kochihibiki	69	1575	54	208	6.7	399	83	0.32	4.4	505	3.3
Takanari	73	1869	25	208	7.3	239	200	0.30	8.9	619	0.5
IR36	77	1654	35	228	6.2	445	101	0.26	5.1	504	4
IR72	77	1698	122	182	6.0	395	122	0.29	8.7	498	4

^aCounted from transplanting. ^bAll data are shown on a dry weight basis. ^cSD= standard deviation. ^dMeasured at heading stage. ^ePartitioning ratio of dry weight to leaf blade. ^fNonstructural carbohydrate content in culm at maturity. ^gDry weight increase during ripening phase. ^hScored on a 0-4 scale where 0 = no lodging and 4 = hardly lodged.

Table 2. Economic yield and yield components of new plant type lines. Tsukuba, Japan. 1994.

Cultivar/line	Spikelet number (no. m ⁻²)	Grain fill ^a (%)	Grain weight ^b (g m ⁻²)	Sink size ^{b,c} (g m ⁻²)	Economic yield ^b (g m ⁻²)	SD ^d	Harvest index ^e
<i>May transplanting</i>							
IR65598-112-2	528	44.9	20.9	1104	495	48	0.25
IR66740-AC1-3	414	37.2	23.3	965	359	78	0.20
Kochihibiki	347	71.1	23.1	802	570	16	0.32
Takanari	511	88.5	21.5	1099	972	19	0.42
IR36	513	80	19.8	1016	813	15	0.39
IR72	547	62	20.0	952	590	52	0.34
<i>June transplanting</i>							
IR65598-112-2	385	49.7	22.3	859	427	7	0.25
IR66740-AC1-3	372	36.6	24.1	897	328	28	0.18
Kochihibiki	330	81	24.1	795	644	61	0.36
Takanari	479	83.4	20.9	1001	835	28	0.39
IR36	451	84.5	19.7	888	751	16	0.39
IR72	482	72.4	20.8	1003	726	41	0.37

^aPercentage of grains that sunk in water total spikelet⁻¹. ^bShown on a brown rice basis at 15% moisture content. The multiplication of grain or kernel weight and spikelet number m⁻². ^cSD = standard deviation. ^eHarvest index = brown rice yield/biological yield.

inactivated along with the wider variation in the weight of fertilized kernels and increased nonstructural carbohydrate content in the culm at maturity (Table 1).

Another factor was less dry weight increase during ripening, characterized by a higher dry weight at heading due to the larger partitioning of dry weight to leaves, especially in IR66740-ACI-3.

These results indicate that panicle weight type rice may not always be high-yielding unless accompanied by an effective grain sink. Less inactivation of the grain sink of NPT lines would ensure a yield level similar to that of IR72. For further increase in potential yield, a higher biological yield—similar to that of Takanari—will be essential. □

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Breaking seed dormancy in different leguminous forage species

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Clitoria (*Clitoria ternatea* L.), *crotalaria* (*Crotalaria juncea* L.), *siratro* (*Macropodium atripurpureum* [DC] Urb.), and

desmanthus (*Desmanthus virgatus* (L.) Willd) have potential as leguminous green manures for rainfed lowland fields after the main rice crop in the Philippines. But their thick, hard seed coverings can cause problems for germination. To break seed dormancy, we subjected the seeds to a treatment of H₂SO₄ (commercial grade, 96%) for 15 min and to scrubbing for 15 min with sand, using mild force. The experiment was replicated three times.

Seed germination was 98.0% for *clitoria* and 95.3% for *siratro* with the H₂SO₄ treatment, which was considerably higher than sand scrubbing and for the control

(Table 1). In *crotalaria*, seed germination was 99.3% without any treatment, 97.3% with sand, and 89.3% with H₂SO₄. *Desmanthus* did not respond well to any of the treatments; the highest germination was 17.3% with sand scrubbing. The seeds did not survive the H₂SO₄ treatment.

To improve the germination of *desmanthus*, we conducted another experiment using various treatments (Table 2). Treating the seeds with H₂SO₄ for 8 min increased the germination to 87.3%. The seeds must be washed very quickly after treatment to prevent them from being subjected to a temperature of more than